

A Rare Combination of Ligamentous Injuries Around the Knee Accompanying Femoral Fracture - A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

High energy injuries, such as motor vehicle accidents are often the cause of femoral shaft fractures. Not very often, femoral fractures can be accompanied with knee ligamentous injuries that are very often underestimated. We present a case of a 20-year-old patient with femoral fracture and a rare combination of ligamentous injuries. Patellar tendon, medial patellofemoral ligament and medial meniscus injuries were not initially detected. Delayed treatment of the ligamentous injuries leads to a poor outcome because of the severe stiffness of the knee. As a result, a very detailed examination and sometimes an MRI evaluation are necessary for an ideal treatment option planning.

Keywords: Injuries; Knee; Femoral fracture

INTRODUCTION

The fractures of the femur are usually result of high energy injuries such as motor vehicle accidents. The surgeons usually focus in the fracture fixation and additionally, the inability of clinical examination of the knee easily leads us to underestimate ligamentous injuries^[1]. Sometimes, rare combinations of ligamentous injuries around the knee can accompany a femoral fracture.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 20-year-old man presented to our hospital after a motor vehicle accident with femoral pain, swelling and leg shortening. After initial evaluation, a transverse femoral shaft fracture was revealed. Because of the pain and the rotational deformity of the leg, the patient could not undergo a full radiographic evaluation. After two hours, the patient underwent an open reduction and internal fixation with plate and screws. The first postoperative day, a

lateral subluxation of the patella was clinically detected and conservative treatment with an extension cast was decided. After six weeks, the knee cast was removed and a rehabilitation protocol started. Because of severe disability in knee flexion, a further evaluation with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was performed. The MRI revealed a complete rupture of medial patellofemoral ligament (mpfl), lateral dislocation of the patella, complete rupture of the patellar tendon and a bucket handle tear of the medial meniscus (Figure 1).

Figure 1: MRI study highlights a medial meniscus bucket handle tear, patella tendon rupture and patella dislocation with mpfl rupture

The patient, three months after the initial injury underwent an arthroscopic, partial, medial meniscectomy, patellar tendon reconstruction with hamstrings autograft with medialization of the tibial insertion of the tendon, lateral retinacular release and medial plication for centralization of the patella (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Intraoperative images showing the patellar tendon reconstruction technique with hamstrings tendon autograft.

The patient had an uneventful postoperative period with no infection or other complication. However, a knee cast in full extension was necessary in order to secure the patellar tendon reconstruction (Figure 3). As a result, six weeks after, although a good healing of the patellar tendon had achieved the patient presented severe stiffness of the knee. An aggressive rehabilitation protocol was followed with poor result. Now, the patient is scheduled for

an operative symphysiolysis and mobilization of the rectus femoris muscle in order a functional range of motion to be achieved.

Figure 3: Final postoperative plain radiograph

DISCUSSION

Concomitant ligamentous and meniscal knee injuries pose a significant clinical dilemma when occurring alongside femoral shaft fractures. Mohammad K. E. Meybodi et al conducted a cross-sectional study of patients with femoral fractures who underwent multiple approaches. Ligamentous and meniscal injuries identification in these patients demands clinical examination combined with imaging modalities such as MRI. Management strategies for these injuries require a multidisciplinary approach. Surgical intervention may be indicated in many cases, involving fracture fixation (e.g. intramedullary nail, external fixation, internal fixation with plates) along with repair or replacement of the damaged ligaments and menisci. Non-operative measures, including immobilization, bracing, and targeted rehabilitation, may also contribute to favourable outcomes and facilitate the patient's recovery^[1].

E. Carlos Rodriguez-Merchan et al executed research involving patients with femoral shaft fractures. In this case study, it is emphasized the importance of identification of occult injuries, such as concomitant fractures or injuries to the pelvis, hip, knee, or adjacent soft tissues, associated with femoral shaft fractures. Delayed recognition of these injuries can lead to complications like nonunion, malunion, or neurovascular compromise. Treatment of femoral shaft may include both surgical and non-surgical approaches, like intramedullary nailing or external fixation. Concurrently addressing associated injuries is essential to minimize complications and optimize outcomes, underscoring the need for understanding occult injuries for comprehensive care in femoral shaft fractures^[2].

Initially undetected knee injuries (e.g. ligamentous tears, meniscal injuries, or fractures of the patella or tibial plateau) accompanying femoral shaft fractures can vary in severity, which depends on factors such as the mechanism of injury, the force applied, and the patient's overall musculoskeletal health and often carry implications for patient.

Therefore, A. Auffarth et al highlight that detailed evaluation, including physical examination and imaging studies, is crucial for optimizing patient outcomes and long-term complications. In this case study, all patients were treated by intramedullary femoral nailing. Knee injuries were diagnosed during follow-up and often lead to chronic pain, instability, and functional limitations if left untreated^[3].

E. H. Becker et al conducted a retrospective analysis of patients with multi-ligamentous knee injuries and associated injuries. They included patients who sustained injuries in two or more ligaments in the knee joint, such as anterior cruciate ligament (ACL), posterior cruciate ligament (PCL), medial collateral ligament (MCL), and lateral collateral ligament (LCL). In addition, the authors might have identified a range of associated injuries such as meniscal tears, fractures, and vascular or neurological injuries, highlighting the complexity and severity of multi-ligamentous knee injuries. Treatment strategies varied, with some patients managed conservatively while others underwent surgical intervention. The outcomes of the study provided valuable insights into the epidemiology, clinical characteristics, and management of these injuries, and potentially offering guidance for healthcare professionals when making treatment decisions^[4].

Byun SE et al conducted a retrospective analysis of 429 femoral shaft injuries to examine the incidence and risk factors of knee injuries occurring simultaneously with ipsilateral femoral shaft fractures. The most common knee injuries included ligament injuries (e.g. ACL or PCL injuries), meniscal tears, and fractures of the distal femur or proximal tibia. The risk factors involved high-energy trauma, open fractures, and comminuted fractures. They highlighted the necessity for rigorous evaluation of the knee joint in patients with femoral shaft fractures and consideration of proper diagnostic and treatment strategies for associated knee injuries^[5].

D. M. Walker et al did a retrospective review of 52 patients with femoral midshaft fractures which were surgically treated. They highlighted the incidence of associated occult knee ligament injuries, which were found during follow-up. The most common ligament damaged in these patients was anterior cruciate ligament (ACL), followed by medial collateral ligament (MCL). The patients felt notable instability, and there was obvious atrophy of the

affected legs. Therefore, they suggested that an overall examination of both knees in the emergency room could reveal at least one major ligamentous injury^[6].

M. J. Szalay et al reviewed 33 patients with ipsilateral femoral and tibial shaft fractures. All these fractures were caused by a high-energy accident. Methods of treatment were both operative (intramedullary nail, internal fixation, external fixation) and non-operative. During follow-up, most patients showed with knee laxity, especially anterior rotary laxity in patients with ipsilateral femoral and tibial shaft fractures, causing noticeable knee instability. Laxity of the posterior structures was most common in femoral shaft fractures alone. Consequently, they recommended performing a thorough assessment involving the rotation of the knee while the patient is under anesthesia for all cases presenting with femoral shaft fractures^[7].

An international analysis was conducted by C. D. Weber et al, in which they revealed the risk factors of associated knee ligamentous injuries in severely injured patients. During the study period, among 139,462 patients, 4411 experienced knee injuries, including 0,8% who suffered from multi-ligamentous injuries linked to knee dislocation. Road traffic accidents, motor vehicle and motorcycle accidents, were responsible for the majority (84.8%) of these injuries. The study emphasizes the need for a comprehensive assessment of associated injuries, especially in lower extremity and chest, in patients with ligamentous knee injuries, even of the knee injury isn't initially obvious. Furthermore, it identifies higher occurrence of popliteal artery injuries linked to knee ligamentous injuries^[8].

The utilization of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in assessing knee injuries following ipsilateral femoral shaft fractures is paramount, as underscored by M. F. Blacksin et al and K. F. Dickson et al in their reviews. MRI plays a pivotal role in detecting internal derangements within the knee joint, including ligamentous tears, meniscal lesions, and cartilage damage, frequently accompanying such fractures. Its meticulous visualization capabilities enable clinicians to accurately diagnose and characterize knee injuries, thereby guiding judicious treatment planning and enhancing patient outcomes. The importance of MRI lies in its ability to offer a comprehensive evaluation extending beyond the primary fracture site, facilitating the early diagnosis of associated knee injuries. This enables the clinicians to tailor treatments for both the femoral shaft fracture and following knee injuries, optimizing care and promoting long-term joint health and function^[9,10].

In our case, the initial evaluation with plain radiographs and the limited clinical examination due to the pain lead us to underestimate the injury. Focusing to the fracture, the ligamentous injuries were not revealed. The surgical treatment of neglected ligamentous injuries such as in our case, cannot achieve an ideal result and multiple operations have to be performed for an acceptable outcome.

CONCLUSION

Femoral fractures can be accompanied with knee ligamentous injuries. Although this is not a very often entity, the surgeons have to be highly suspicious because delayed treatment of these injuries has poor results and multiple operations are required for an acceptable outcome.

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